

GENERAL PURPOSE PROGRAMMING PYTHON

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It retains the benefits of the Charm++ runtime, including dynamic load balancing, asynchronous execution model with automatic overlap of communication and computation, high performance, and scalability from laptops to supercomputers. By being Pythonbased, CharmPy also benefits from modern language features, access to popular scientific computing and data science software, and interoperability with existing technologies like C, Fortran and OpenMP. To illustrate the simplicity of the model, we will show how to implement

ABSTRACT

Parallel programming can be extremely challenging. Programming models have been proposed to simplify this task, but wide acceptance of these remains elusive for many reasons, including the demand for greater accessibility and productivity. In this paper, we introduce a parallel programming model and framework called CharmPy, based on the Python language. CharmPy builds on Charm++, and runs on top of its C++ runtime. It presents several unique features in the form of a simplified model and API, increased flexibility, and the ability to write everything in Python. CharmPy is a high-level model based on the paradigm of distributed migratable objects.

a distributed parallel map function based on the Master-Worker pattern using CharmPy, with support for asynchronous concurrent jobs. We also present performance results running stencil code and molecular dynamics mini-apps fully written in Python, on Blue Waters and Cori supercomputers. For stencil3d, we show performance similar to an equivalent MPI-based program, and significantly improved performance for imbalanced computations. Using Numba to JIT-compile the critical parts of the code, we show performance for

both miniapps similar to the equivalent C++ code. Index Terms—programming model, parallel programming, distributed computing, multiprocessing, Python, HPC

INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Effective and productive programming of parallel machines can be extremely challenging. To this day, it remains hard to find programming models and frameworks that are considered accessible and productive by a wide range of users, support a variety of use cases, and achieve good performance and scalability on a wide range of systems. There is demand from programmers across various domains to write parallel applications, but they are neither computer scientists nor expert programmers. This often leads to their need to rely on experts to implement their ideas, settle for suboptimal (sometimes serial) performance, or to develop codes that are difficult to scale, maintain and extend. A programming model must meet several demands to overcome these challenges, including: (a) accessibility (easy to approach, learn and use); (b) productivity; (c) provide highlevel abstractions that can hide the details of the underlying hardware and network; (d) achieve good parallel performance; (e) make efficient use of resources in heterogeneous environments; (f) portability; (g) easy to integrate with existing software. The productivity of a language and programming model, in particular, can be a critical factor for the successful development of a software project, and for its continued longterm evolution. In the realm of High-performance Computing (HPC), MPI combined with C/C++ or Fortran is widely used. Reasons for this include performance/scalability, the perceived sustainability of these technologies, and the existence of large legacy codebases. However, though important building-blocks, these technologies by themselves present important limitations towards achieving the

above goals. C++ and Fortran are arguably not introductory-level programming languages. MPI provides message passing and synchronization primitives, but lacks high-level features like hardware abstractions, dynamic resource allocation, work scheduling; and is not particularly suited for execution of asynchronous events, or applications with load imbalance and irregular communication patterns. Many parallel programming languages and runtimes have been developed in the last two decades [1], with modern ones providing high-level abstractions, task-based runtimes, global address spaces, adaptive load balancing, and messagedriven execution. Examples of modern languages and runtimes include Chapel [2], X10 [3], UPC [4], Legion [5], HPX [6] and Charm++ [7]. In spite of this, MPI remains by all appearances the de facto standard for parallel programming in the HPC field. Analyzing the causes of this is outside the scope of this paper, but we believe that, although these models provide powerful abstractions, scalability and performance, obstacles for adoption include either a real or perceived lack of accessibility, productivity, generality, interoperability and sustainability. Charm++ has enjoyed success with several large applications running on supercomputers [8]–[10], but can be improved in terms of some of these aspects. Parallel programming frameworks based on Python have emerged in recent years (e.g. Dask [11] and Ray [12]). Although aimed at productivity, they tend to have limited performance and scalability, and applicability only to specific use cases (e.g. task scheduling, MapReduce, data analytics). In this paper, we introduce a general-purpose parallel programming model and distributed computing framework called CharmPy, which builds on Charm++, and is aimed at overcoming these challenges. One of its distinguishing features is that it uses the

Python programming language, one of the most popular languages in use today [13] together with C, C++ and Java. Python has become very popular for scientific computing, data science and machine learning, as evidenced by software like NumPy, SciPy, pandas, TensorFlow and scikit-learn. It is also very effective for integrating existing technologies like C, Fortran and OpenMP code. Its popularity and ease of use [14] helps to avoid the barrier of adopting a new language, and enables straightforward compatibility with many established software packages. In addition, the development of technologies like NumPy [15], Numba [16], [17] and Cython [18] presents a compelling case for the use of Python as a high-level language driving native machine-optimized code. Using these technologies, it is possible to express a program in Python using high-level concepts, and have the critical parts (or even the bulk of it) be compiled and run natively. CharmPy runs on top of Charm++ [7], [19], a C++ runtime, but it is not a simple Python binding for it. Indeed, CharmPy's programming model is simpler and provides unique features that simplify the task of writing parallel applications, while retaining the runtime capabilities of Charm++. For example, Charm++ developers have to write special interface files for each distributed object type; these files have to be processed by a special translator that generates C++ code. In addition, the Structured Dagger [20] language is often necessary for expression of control flow and message order. With CharmPy, all of the code can be written in Python, and no specialized language, preprocessing or compilation steps are necessary to run an application. CharmPy also benefits from high-level features of Python, like automatic memory management and object serialization.

With CharmPy, we want to meet the following goals:

- Simple, high-level programming model.
- Based on the widely used Python programming language, equipped with modern features and extensive libraries.
- General-purpose: supporting a wide range of applications, including those with embarrassingly parallel workloads, and complex scientific simulations running on supercomputers.
- High-performance: capable of achieving performance comparable to C++ parallel applications.
- Scalable from small devices to supercomputers.
- Programming and execution model with inherent communication and computation overlap.
- Adaptive runtime features, e.g. dynamic load balancing and automatic communication/computation overlap.

The achievement of some of these goals can be hard to quantify, relying in some cases on subjective assessment. We will present a use case to demonstrate the simplicity in terms of amount of code, readability and code complexity required to implement a non-trivial worker pool that can run multiple independent map functions on multiple nodes with dynamic load balancing, using the well-known master-worker pattern. We discuss the limitations of implementing the same use case with MPI. We will also show that parallel applications can be written with CharmPy that are comparable in terms of performance and scalability to applications using MPI or written in C++. This is possible even with applications fully written in Python, by using technologies like Numba. Python and Charm++ are both highly portable, and CharmPy runs on Unix, Windows, macOS and many supercomputer environments. The code is public and open-source [21]. The rest

of the paper is organized as follows. In section II we explain the CharmPy programming model. Section III presents the parallel map use case. Section IV covers runtime implementation details. In section V we present performance results. Finally, in section VI we conclude the paper.

THE CHARMPY PROGRAMMING MODEL In this section, we explain the main concepts of the CharmPy programming model, beginning with an overview of the programming paradigm and its execution model.

A. Overview

CharmPy is based on the paradigm of distributed migratable objects with asynchronous remote method invocation. A program is expressed in terms of objects and the interactions between them. There can exist multiple distributed objects per processing element (PE); these objects can communicate with any other distributed object in the system via remote method invocation, which involves message passing. Objects are not bound to a specific PE and can migrate between PEs without affecting application code. Parallel decomposition is therefore based on objects rather than system resources, which has the benefit of enabling more natural decomposition, abstraction from hardware, and gives the runtime flexibility to balance load, schedule work, and overlap computation and communication. In the asynchronous execution model, a process does not block waiting for a remote method to complete, and the runtime can automatically continue scheduling other work during that time (which is facilitated by the presence of multiple objects per PE). Similarly, there are

no blocking receives, and the runtime schedules delivery of messages as they become available. All of this serves to hide latency and enables the automatic overlap of communication and computation. Another benefit of object-based decomposition, where an arbitrary number of objects per process can exist, is that it allows for tunable fine-grained decomposition without affecting the structure of the program. A fine-grained decomposition is particularly beneficial in irregular applications and those with load imbalance (the performance results in section V show an example of this). The execution model on which CharmPy is based, including its benefits, has been described in detail and demonstrated in previous works [7]. In the rest of this section we will focus on the CharmPy programming model and API.

B. Chare: the distributed object In CharmPy, there is a class named Chare that represents distributed objects. To define a new distributed object type, the user simply defines a new class that inherits from Chare, e.g. `class MyChare(Chare): ...`. Any methods of the new chare type will be callable remotely using regular Python method invocation syntax. Chares can be created at any point after runtime initialization. The runtime is represented by an object called charm that exists on every process, and is initialized by calling `charm.start()`. After initialization, control is handed to the application via a user-defined function or chare, known as entry point, that runs on one processor (typically PE 0). For example, the following is a complete program that creates a single chare, calls one of its methods, and exits after the method has been executed:


```
1  from charmpy import *
2
3  class MyChare (Chare) :
4      def SayHi (self, msg) :
5          print (msg)
6          charm.exit ()
7
8  def main (args) :
9      proxy = Chare (MyChare, onPE=-1)
10     proxy.SayHi ('Hello')
11
12  charm.start (main)
```

This program can be run on multiple processes. Line 12 starts the CharmPy runtime on each process, and indicates that the function called `main` will be the entry point. In line 9, a single chare is created. The runtime can create the chare on any PE, because the application did not specify any. The call to create a chare returns a special object called proxy. Proxies are used to invoke methods remotely, and have the same methods as the chare that they reference. In this example, the method `SayHi` is called via the proxy. Remote method invocation is explained in detail in section II-D. Finally, the parallel program is finalized with a call to `charm.exit()`.

C. Waiting for events

1) Threaded entry methods: In CharmPy, entry methods can run in their own thread when tagged with the `@threaded` decorator⁴. This allows pausing the execution of the entry method to wait for certain events. While the thread is paused, the runtime can continue scheduling other

work in the same process. Threaded entry methods enable writing asynchronous applications in direct-style programming, simplifying expression of control flow. More specifically, it enables the two mechanisms described next.

2) Wait for chare state: The wait construct provides a convenient way to suspend execution inside a chare's entry method until the chare reaches a specific state. The syntax is: `self.wait ('condition')`

where condition is a string specifying a Python conditional statement, which is meant to evaluate the chare's state. Reaching this state will generally depend on the interaction of the chare with other chares. As an example, consider the following use case, where a chare performs an iterative computation. In each iteration, the chare sends data to a set of chares, waits to receive data from the same chares and subsequently performs a computation. The code is shown below:


```
1  @threaded
2  def work(self):
3      for iteration in range(NUM_ITERATIONS):
4          for nb in self.neighbors:
5              nb.recvData(...)
6              self.wait(
7                  'self.msg_count == len(self.neighbors)')
8              self.msg_count = 0
9              self.do_computation()
10
11 def recvData(self, data):
12     self.msg_count += 1
13     # ... process data ...
```

Note that, to suspend control flow, the caller must be running within the context of a threaded entry method⁵.

3) Futures: A future [22] is an object that acts as a proxy for a result that is initially unknown. Futures are present in many modern programming languages. In CharmPy, they are evaluated asynchronously, and will only block when the creator attempts to retrieve the value.

As explained in section II-D, futures can be used to query the result of remote calls. In addition, CharmPy allows futures to be created explicitly, sent to other chares, and be used to wait until an arbitrary operation (possibly involving multiple chares, and sequence of remote method invocations and reductions) has been completed. Chares in possession of the future can use it to send a value to the waiting chare. For example

:

```
1  @threaded
2  def start(self):
3      f1 = charm.createFuture()
4      f2 = charm.createFuture()
5      remoteChare.doWork(f1, f2)
6      # ... do other work ...
7      print('Value of future 1 is', f1.get())
8      print('Value of future 2 is', f2.get())
9
10 def doWork(self, f1, f2):
11     # ...
12     f1.send(x) # send value to future 1
13     # ...
14     f2.send(y) # send value to future 2
```


Futures can also be used as reduction targets:

```
1  class Worker (Chare) :
2      def doWork (self, done_future) :
3          x = ...
4          self.contribute (x, Reducer.sum, done_future)
5
6  def main (args) :
7      # create 100 workers
8      workers = Array (Worker, 100)
9      result = charm.createFuture ()
10     workers.doWork (result)
11     # wait for work to complete and final reduction
12     print ('Reduction result is', result.get ())
13     charm.exit ()
14
15 charm.start (main)
```

Chare migration

Chares can migrate from one process to another. Reasons for migrating chares usually have to do with resource management, for example:

- Place communicating chares in the same process, host, or nearby host, to minimize latency and maximize bandwidth.
- Balance computational load, particularly if the workload of chares is not homogeneous.

The most common scenario is to let the runtime migrate chares where it considers appropriate, and the application only needs to signal the runtime at suitable points during execution at which to do this. However, chares can also be manually moved to a PE of the user's choice by calling:

```
self.migrate(toPe)
```

The runtime takes care of serializing the object, migrating it to the new location and ensuring that messages directed to the object keep getting delivered [7]. CharmPy

uses the pickle library to serialize chares, which by default attempts to serialize all of the attributes of the chare (which must be pickable). The application can customize what gets pickled (and in what form), by defining the `__getstate__` and `__setstate__` methods [23].

F. Reductions

Reductions are one of the most common collective operations in CharmPy, and are used to apply a reduction function (also known as reducer) to a set of data that is distributed among the chares in a collection. CharmPy internally leverages the reduction framework in Charm++ to perform reductions in a distributed, asynchronous and scalable manner. The general syntax to perform a reduction is: `self.contribute(data, reducer, target)`

To do a reduction, all of the chares in a collection must call this method. Here, data is the data contributed by the chare for reduction. The reducer is the function that is applied to the set of contributed data.

CharmPy provides several builtin reducers (including sum, max, min, product, gather), and allows users to easily define their own reducers. The target parameter determines who receives the result of the reduction. It can be a method of a chare or set of chares, specified using the syntax `proxy.method` where proxy can reference any individual chare or collection of chares (in the latter case the result is broadcast to all the members). The target can also be a future (see section II-H3). It is worth noting that reductions are asynchronous, i.e. chares do not block waiting for reductions to

complete, and there can be multiple reductions in flight (even for the same chare collection) at a given time. An empty reduction can be performed by passing `data=None` and `reducer=None`. Empty reductions are useful for determining when a group of chares have reached a certain point in the application, and are typically used as a synchronization mechanism.

The following is a simple example of a sum reduction performed by members of a chare array, with the result being sent to element 0 of the array:

```
1 class Worker(Chare):
2
3     def work(self, data):
4         data = numpy.arange(20)
5         self.contribute(data, Reducer.sum,
6                         self.thisProxy[0].getResult)
7
8     def getResult(self, result):
9         print("Reduction result is", result)
10        charm.exit()
11
12 def main(args):
13     # create 100 workers
14     array = Array(Worker, 100)
15     array.work()
16
17 charm.start(main)
```

1) Custom reducers: Users can also define their own reducer functions in CharmPy. The reducer function must take a single parameter which is a list of contributions (each from a different chare), and return the result of reducing the contributions. Registration of the reducer with CharmPy

is done by calling `Reducer.addReducer(myReducerFunc)`.

The map function is a feature in many programming languages that applies a given function to each element of a list, returning a list of results in the same order. Map can be implemented in parallel by

applying the function to different inputs in parallel, collecting the results, and returning them to the caller. Python's multiprocessing library [24] implements a parallel version, however it is limited to a single node. In this section, we will show how to implement a distributed parallel version that can run on multiple nodes using CharmPy. The implementation uses the well-known Master-Worker pattern.

We will call each item of the input list a task. The master can coordinate multiple independent map jobs at the same time (which can be launched at different times), and is in charge of dynamically giving tasks to idle workers, thus ensuring that load balancing is achieved even in cases where tasks have disparate workloads. First we show how the user-facing API looks:

```
1  def f(x):
2      return x*x
3
4  def main(args):
5      pool = Chare(MapManager, onPE=0)
6      f1 = charm.createFuture()
7      f2 = charm.createFuture()
8      tasks1 = [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]
9      tasks2 = [1, 3, 5, 7, 9]
10     pool.map_async(f, 2, tasks1, f1)
11     pool.map_async(f, 2, tasks2, f2)
12     print("Final results are", f1.get(), f2.get())
13     charm.exit()
14
15 charm.start(main)
```

In this example, the main function creates a single master chare on PE 0, which will coordinate the pool of workers (line 5). It launches two separate jobs at the same time, to apply function *f* to two different lists of items. A map job is initiated by calling the method `map_async` of the master, which receives the function to apply, the desired number of processors to use for the job, the list of tasks, and the

future where the end result must be placed. It will block on line 12 waiting for the result of both jobs to arrive. Now we will show how the master and workers are implemented⁶). A worker is a chare that has a `start` method used to signal the start of a new job. The method receives the job ID, the function to apply, the list of tasks in the job, and a proxy to the master. The code for workers is shown below:


```
1 class Worker(Chare):
2
3     def start(self, job_id, f, tasks, master):
4         self.job_id = job_id
5         self.func = f
6         self.tasks = tasks
7         self.master = master
8         # request a new task
9         master.getTask(self.thisIndex, job_id)
10
11     def apply(self, task_id):
12         result = self.func(self.tasks[task_id])
13         self.master.getTask(self.thisIndex,
14                             self.job_id, task_id,
15                             result)
```

In addition, workers have a method called `apply` that receives a task ID and applies the function to the specified task (line 12). Subsequently, it calls the method `getTask` of the master (line 13) to request a new task. The arguments are the `chare`'s index in the

collection of workers (used to identify the worker), the job ID, and the ID and result of the last executed task (note how the previous result is sent at the same time as a new task is requested). Next, we show the code for the master:

```
1 class MapManager(Chare):
2
3     def __init__(self):
4         # create a Worker in every processor
5         self.workers = Group(Worker)
6         self.free_procs = set(range(1,
7                                   charm.numPes()))
8         self.next_job_id = 0
9         self.jobs = {}
10
11     def map_async(self, func, numProcs, tasks,
12                 future):
13         """start a new map job"""
14         # select free processors
15         free = [self.free_procs.pop()
16                for i in range(numProcs)]
17         job = self.addJob(tasks, free, future)
18         # tell workers in free processors to start
19         for p in free:
20             self.workers[p].start(job.id, func, tasks,
21                                   self.thisProxy)
```

When the master is instantiated, it creates one worker on every PE by using a `Group` (line 5). It also initializes a set that is used to track

which processors are not executing any job (line 6). When a new map job is requested via the `map_async` method, the master selects the

requested number of free processors, stores the job information and signals the workers

on the selected processors to start.

```
23     def getTask(self, src, job_id, prev_task=None,
24                 prev_result=None):
25         """called by worker to get a new task"""
26         job = self.jobs[job_id]
27         if prev_task is not None:
28             job.addResult(prev_task, prev_result)
29         if not job.isDone():
30             next_task = job.nextTask()
31             if next_task is not None:
32                 self.workers[src].apply(next_task)
33         else:
34             for p in job.procs: self.free_procs.add(p)
35             self.removeJob(job)
36             job.future.send(job.results)
```

Workers will begin requesting tasks by calling the method `getTask` of the master. This method simply stores the result provided by the worker, and sends a new task if there are more tasks to complete. If the job is done, it sends the result to the future that was provided by the user. The full program is less than 100 lines of code and is available in the CharmPy source code repository. Although a functionally equivalent program can technically be implemented using MPI, it requires a non-trivial amount of low-level code, more so if we want an API that is similar in terms of simplicity. Required low-level code would include: (a) asynchronous communication;

(b) ability to receive messages of different types, from any source, at any time, and deliver to multiple destinations in a given process; (c) threads. To illustrate this, note how PE 0 executes both the main function and the Master chore. At one point, the main function is waiting for two types of events (to receive the value of futures `f1` and `f2`, being unknown which one will arrive first or from which process). At the same time, the master chore needs to process messages from any worker asking for new tasks, and could also receive messages asking to start new jobs (`map async`)

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